

Coordination Chemistry of Technetium as Related to Nuclear Medicine

S. C. SRIVASTAVA* and P. RICHARDS

Medical Department, Brookhaven National Laboratory, Upton, New York 11973, U.S.A.

Significant advances have been made in the area of technetium coordination chemistry during the last five years. The main driving force behind this recent surge of interest in the field has been due to the practical application of technetium-99m in the rapidly growing speciality of nuclear medicine. Technetium-99 is one of the products of nuclear fission reactions, but it was the development of the molybdenum-99-technetium-99m generator about two decades ago that provided the basis for the development of radiopharmaceuticals routinely used in modern diagnostic applications. The chemistry of this element has proven to be quite rich owing to its multiple oxidation states and variable geometry; this can be attributed to its position in the middle of the periodic table. Diagnostic radiopharmaceuticals comprise predominantly III, IV and V oxidation states of Tc and involve a variety of coordination complexes. Even though the chemistry of Tc has been slow to evolve, recent synthetic advances have provided a more scientific basis for the study of a number of compounds with diverse coordination geometries and structures. Ligands with oxygen, nitrogen, and sulfur donor atoms have been utilized to elucidate various aspects of the coordination chemistry of Tc. Single crystal X-ray structural analysis has been extensively used to characterize Tc complexes and thus construct a firm foundation for the study of synthetic and mechanistic aspects of the chemistry of this element.

EVEN though technetium has been observed in some stellar materials and despite some evidence suggesting that a continuous production of the element is taking place in the universe¹, evidence for the occurrence of primordial terrestrial technetium has not yet materialized despite the extensive searches using sophisticated radiochemical procedures. On a geological time scale, all isotopes of this element are unstable and thus throughout the early history of chemistry, no technetium was available for study. Artificial production of technetium in minute quantities was reported by Perrier and Segre in 1937², and chemical quantities became available in the early 1960's (ca \$3000/g). At the present time ⁹⁹Tc is produced in kilogram amounts as a fission product and is available at about \$50 per g. ⁹⁹Tc is a soft beta emitter (β^- max 0.292 MeV) with a 2.13×10^6 yr half-life and thus presents only a minor radiation hazard. Milligram quantities can safely be manipulated by following a few simple precautions. Virtually all chemical studies so far have employed ⁹⁹Tc.

Since the mid 1970's there has been a dramatic surge of activity in the area of synthetic and structural chemistry of technetium. This is attributable to the desire of inorganic chemists to acquire a basic understanding of the chemistry of this sparsely studied element. A very great driving force has been provided by the widespread use of technetium-99m in diagnostic nuclear medicine procedures and by the ever growing realization that further advances in the area of ^{99m}Tc radiopharmaceuticals will greatly depend on basic research effort on solution chemistry, coordination complexes, and mechanistic studies of Tc compounds³.

Uses in nuclear medicine :

To carry out diagnostic nuclear medicine procedures, a "radiopharmaceutical" (some chemical form of a gamma emitting radionuclide) is injected into a patient and the biodistribution of the radiopharmaceutical is monitored by suitable external imaging devices such as a gamma camera. Among the few radionuclides available for these applications, ^{99m}Tc has, by far, the optimum properties and is clearly the "ideal" radiotracer⁴. The monoenergetic gamma emission of 140 keV is well suited for use with the present day gamma cameras. This energy provides excellent penetration from deep seated organs in the body and the loss during collimation is minimal. A total lack of beta emission results in the absence of unnecessary absorbed radiation dose to the patient. The 6.02 hr half-life cuts down the radiation dose further by minimizing continued patient exposure after completion of the diagnostic procedure. Because of reduced radiation dose, large amounts of radioactivity can be administered in order to provide good resolution and increased information content in the collected images. Very frequent repetition of studies is also facilitated. ^{99m}Tc is inexpensive and is readily available as ^{99m}TcO₄⁻ with the advent of the ⁹⁹Mo/^{99m}Tc generator^{5,6}. Of equal importance is the fact that the varied chemistry of technetium in its many oxidation states allows the incorporation of ^{99m}Tc into a variety of radiopharmaceuticals that are specific for different organs³. Without the possibility of appropriate chemical manipulations, the preeminence of ^{99m}Tc among the medically useful radionuclides would not have been established. The use of ^{99m}Tc for diagnosis has proven so successful

polarography, pulse polarography and cyclic voltammetry, etc. In addition, allied techniques such as coulometry and amperometry have also been utilized. Despite the fact that most technetium reductions at the dropping mercury electrode are usually irreversible, polarographic techniques have afforded a means of establishing the oxidation states which are stabilized in various media. Despite a large early literature on the polarographic reduction of technetium³, considerable confusion exists as to the exact number of electrons involved in the various reduction processes. The initial 3- or 4-electron reduction waves occur in acidic media at sufficiently positive potentials providing satisfactory data. Results are unreliable in the presence of highly acidic solutions; especially HCl, because of the side reactions due to the dissolution of mercury and subsequent reduction of pertechnetate. The data obtained using hydrochloric acid at a concentration of 0.1 M or more as an electrolyte should thus be interpreted with caution. Reductions in buffered acidic media take place in multiple steps. A rather well formed first wave occurs for a diffusion controlled four-electron reduction and it shifts with pH approximately as follows :

$$E_{\frac{1}{2}} = A - 0.10 \text{ pH} \quad (\text{pH } 0 - 7) \quad \dots (1)$$

where A is +0.06, +0.05 and +0.12 V for perchloric, hydrochloric and sulphuric acids, respectively. A subsequent wave at -0.9 V corresponds to the three-electron reduction to the metal :

If the pre-contact of the solution with mercury has not been carefully avoided, the data in hydrochloric and sulphuric acid media often show equal intensity waves I (4e⁻) and II (3e⁻). The relative heights, however, are in better agreement in perchloric acid media. The half-wave potential for the first wave is not affected significantly by the presence of complexing agents, the rate-determining step being :

The HTcO₄⁻ undergoes a rapid sequence of fast reactions to produce technetium(III). Using cyclic voltammetry or anodic-sweep pulse polarography, the technetium(III) can often be reoxidized to technetium(IV) or even technetium(V)¹⁵. The second wave at -0.9 V gives only an upper limit for *n* (electron change) because of the presence of a catalytic component. Further waves occurring at more cathodic potentials are very large and obviously catalytic.

In buffered alkaline media, several waves are also found but the wave heights do not often correspond to integral values of *n*. Several workers have found a rather well defined wave at -0.8 V regardless of the presence of complexing agents¹⁵. It was postulated that a one-electron change resulting in the formation of technetate ion, TcO₄²⁻, an unstable species in water, accounts for the rate-determining step. Non-integral values between 2 and 4 were

reported for the total number of electrons transferred. The second wave at about -0.9 V corresponds to a value of *n* of between 4 and 5. In unbuffered neutral or alkaline media, pertechnetate shows much more complicated behaviour though not too unsimilar to that in buffered alkaline media. It has been proposed that the alkaline environment produced at the electrode surface during pertechnetate reduction accounts for the similarity¹⁵.

Reducing agents :

With the exception of pertechnetate itself, and perhaps technetium-99m-labeled sulphur colloid, all other radiopharmaceuticals contain technetium in an oxidation state lower than seven. Reduction of pertechnetate is thus a prerequisite before achieving successful incorporation of technetium into any of a variety of useful ligands. Pertechnetate itself does not bind to complexing ligands or to any extent with molecules of biomedical interest. When injected intravenously, as for brain imaging, pertechnetate becomes weakly bound to albumin, largely through electrostatic interactions. This binding is not strong and pertechnetate thus bound can be easily displaced by anions such as perchlorate. Pertechnetate solutions can be reduced by many common reducing agents. In principle, any reductant with a reduction potential lower than that of pertechnetate (+0.738 V) is capable of performing the reduction. The pertechnetate ion is a mild oxidizing agent (unlike the strongly oxidizing permanganate) and its reduction is generally favoured in a number of media of interest in nuclear medicine. The production of the insoluble oxide, TcO₂, or a hydrate thereof, however, is thermodynamically favoured in aqueous solutions except in highly acidic media, or in the presence of complexing agents. Formation of the oxide is a competitive pathway in all reduction reactions and has to be avoided in carrying out the preparation of soluble radiopharmaceuticals. Chemistry of the reducing agent also plays a very important role, especially when using metallic reducing agents.

The most frequently used reducing agents include stannous ion, ferric chloride and ascorbic acid, conc. HCl, borohydride and dithionite⁸. Others such as cuprous ion, formamidine sulphinic acid, and sulphhydryl compounds have also been employed. Electrolytic reduction using inert as well as tin or zirconium electrodes can also be employed in some systems. During the preparation of radiopharmaceuticals, reductions are generally carried out in the presence of a complexing ligand (often a compound that one wishes to label with ^{99m}Tc) that stabilizes the lower oxidation state of technetium and thus eliminates or minimizes subsequent hydrolytic reactions. Redox reactions involving pertechnetate most likely proceed via oxygen atom transfer to the reducing agent and are favoured with reductants that react by such a mechanism. The reductions are thermodynamically favoured in general but the kinetic parameters often assume a greater importance. Stannous compounds are employed as

reducing agents in most radiopharmaceutical preparations, despite the various reported problems¹³.

Synthetic and Structural Studies

The last few years have experienced an intense surge of interest in the area of synthesis and structure elucidation of technetium coordination compounds. The fact that technetium has one of the most complicated and subtle chemistries compared to other elements used in nuclear medicine applications is not totally without advantage since the intricate chemistry also offers almost unlimited possibilities of manipulation in order to produce a wide range of complexes with tailor-made properties. Certain lower oxidation states of technetium can be stabilized against subsequent ligand substitution by choosing an appropriate coordination environment, which is expected to make the complexes retain their *in vivo* integrity. Accordingly, the areas of intense research effort recently in controlled syntheses of a wide variety of stable, substitution inert technetium complexes and the elucidation of their structure and chemistry promise to substantially add new and useful agents to our existing armamentarium of ^{99m}Tc radiopharmaceuticals. Additionally, a number of model technetium compounds that have been synthesized no doubt will permit a study of the *in vitro* and *in vivo* reaction mechanisms and thus provide a basis for elucidating structure-activity relationships and consequently aid in the development of new or improved agents for various applications in nuclear medicine. This intensified interest is exemplified by the fact that about five years ago, only a handful of simple technetium compounds had been synthesized and characterized. The structure of these compounds was poorly understood. A number of coordination compounds with technetium in oxidation states ranging from 1+ to 7+ and with coordination numbers from 4 to 8 have since been prepared and structurally characterized by definitive techniques such as single crystal X-ray analysis.

1. Synthesis :

The predominantly used method so far for preparing technetium-99m radiopharmaceuticals is by the so-called redox route, for example, by the stannous reduction of pertechnetate in the presence of a potential complexing ligand. Despite the limitations involved in this method, it has allowed the development of a variety of extremely useful radiopharmaceuticals. Another possible approach is the synthesis of ^{99m}Tc-labeled compounds utilizing ligand substitution reactions, that is by substitution of the desired ligand onto a stable, characterized, prerduced technetium center. This approach is not without disadvantages; however, several advantages become obvious such as a control over the oxidation state and coordination environment of technetium in the final product, synthetic possibilities with a greater variety of ligands and the possibility of manipulating biological selectivity by retaining some ligands and changing others in a methodical manner. While examples of this having been accomplished at

the no-carrier-added level are so far relatively scarce, attempts at carrying out ligand substitution reactions at the carrier technetium level have met with considerable success⁹.

For macroscopic amounts, the substitution route for preparing Tc(V) and Tc(IV) complexes is convenient because of the availability of TcOX₂ and TcX₃²⁻ materials (X=halogen). These reactions are usually conducted in organic solvents such as ethanol or THF in order to prevent disproportionation and hydrolysis of the starting material. Due to the fairly labile nature of the d³ center, the reactions proceed rapidly to yield five-, six- and seven-coordinate complexes with an intact TcO³⁺ core. Under anhydrous conditions the octahedral d³ center, however, is substitutionally inert and somewhat forcing conditions are required to drive the reactions to completion. TcCl₃²⁻ reacts more rapidly than TcI₃²⁻; in aqueous media these compounds are quite labile and produce the insoluble TcO₂. At the no-carrier-added level, well-defined TcOX₂ and TcX₃²⁻ species are not generally accessible. There are several poorly defined technetium-99m complexes however, that have been utilized as substrates for substitution syntheses to produce complexes with glucoheptonate, gluconate, DTPA, citrate and cyclam, etc¹⁴.

(i) *Simple salts and complexes with inorganic ligands* : The heptavalent state is normally most stable in simple salts (e.g. TcO₇⁻) followed by the tetravalent state (e.g. TcO₂). The other oxidation states generally gain stability via complex formation. The oxides, sulphides and simple oxo-anions have all been well characterized. The weakly paramagnetic, volatile heptoxide has a structure consisting of two TcO₄ tetrahedra which share an oxygen atom in a linear Tc-O-Tc array¹⁴. The black TcO₂ with a distorted rutile structure is formed from reduction of TcO₇⁻ by hydrolysis of hexahalogenotechnetate(IV) complexes, or by thermal decomposition of NH₄[TcO₄] at 950° in a nitrogen atmosphere. Several ternary oxides have also been reported, for example NaTcO₃, M₂TcO₃, Li₃TcO₄, Li₄TcO₅ and M₂TcO₆, etc.¹⁷. The sulphides Tc₂S₇ and TcS₂ are isomorphous with the corresponding oxides. The heptasulphide is volatile and can be prepared by addition of H₂S, thioacetamide or thiosulphate to acid solutions of pertechnetate.

Various halides, thiocyanates and oxohalides of technetium are known and have been studied extensively¹⁴. Most of these compounds are not stable in neutral aqueous media and the synthetic schemes involving these as starting materials are carried out in acidic solutions or in non-aqueous solvents. One of the important intermediates is square-pyramidal TcOX₂ which is produced upon reduction of TcO₇⁻ with concentrated halogen acid¹⁸. Octahedral [Tc(NCS)₆]³⁻ and [Tc(NCS)₆]²⁻ have been prepared by the reaction of (NH₄)SCN with a solution of (NH₄)₂[TcX₆] compounds¹⁹. All SCN⁻ ligands are N-bonded and a nearly perfect octahedral symmetry exists for (Bu₄N)₃[Tc(NCS)₆], as demonstrated by X-ray structural studies. Various cyanide

complexes containing the TcO^{3+} , $tr-TcO_3^+$ and $tr-Tc(O)(OMe)^{2+}$ cores have recently been prepared and characterized²⁰. A variety of carbonyl, nitrosyl and organometallic compounds of technetium have been reported in the early as well as recent literature. Also, a range of mixed-ligand Tc(I) complexes of the type $Tc(CO)_5-nL_n$ (L=monodentate organic ligand, e.g. Py, PR_3 or AsR_3) have been synthesized and studied.

(ii) *Coordination complexes containing organic ligands :*

(a) *Oxygen donor ligands :* Complexes of technetium that have been prepared and characterized with this class of ligands include β -diketonates, $[TcCl_4(sal)]$, diphosphonates, etc. The neutral complex $Tc(acac)_3$ has recently been obtained by refluxing TcO_2 in neat acetylacetone^{21,22}. Earlier, it was prepared by refluxing $TcCl_4(PPh_3)_2$ with the ligand in an analogous reaction²³. Reaction of $[PPh_4][TcX_6]$ or $TcX_4(PPh_3)_2$ (X=Cl, Br) with anhydrous acetylacetone under different conditions also produces mixed ligand Tc(III) and Tc(IV) complexes such as $Tc(acac)_2X_2$, $PPh_4[Tc(acac)X_4]$, $Tc(acac)_3-PPh_2X$, etc.^{23,24}. The latter compound displays a *trans* configuration with a coordination polyhedron approximating D_{4h} symmetry based on X-ray structural studies. The reaction of excess methylene diphosphonate (routinely used skeletal imaging agent) with $[TcBr_6]^{2-}$ produces a mixture of species. Purification yields a material that has been shown by X-ray analysis to be polymeric with a Tc/MDP ratio of 1.0²⁴. Each Tc center has an octahedral coordination environment. Two symmetry related Tc atoms are bridged by each MDP ligand and each Tc atom is bound to two symmetry related MDP ligands. Even though the oxidation state of the Tc center cannot be assigned unambiguously, Tc(IV) or Tc(V) appear to be most likely present. Such structures are also likely with the other commonly used diphosphonate bone agents. The actual radiopharmaceuticals (^{99m}Tc-methylene diphosphonate, ^{99m}Tc-ethylidenedihydroxy disodium phosphonate) have recently been shown using HPLC techniques to contain a mixture of species in solution²⁵. The individual components all localize in bone but significant differences exist in their blood clearance, soft tissue uptake and excretion from the body.

(b) *Nitrogen donor ligands :* A variety of complexes of technetium with this class of ligands have recently been synthesized and studied. Examples are $[TcO_2(en)_2]X$ (X=Cl, Br, I), $[TcO_2(cyclam)]ClO_4 \cdot H_2O$, complexes with 1,2-diaminocyclohexane, 1,2-diaminopropane, several pyridine derivatives, and imidazole, TcO_2XL type compounds (where L=bipy, X=Cl, Br or L=phen, X=Cl), $[TcO(HBPz_3)Cl_2]$ [where $HBPz_3$ =hydrotris(1-pyrazolyl)borate] and $[Tc(DMG)_2SnCl_3(OH)] \cdot 3H_2O$ (DMG=dime-thylglyoxime)^{13,14,21,26,27}. Both the ethylenediamine and cyclam complexes contain the $tr-TcO_3^+$ core embedded in an approximately octahedral coordination environment provided by the four nitrogen donor atoms. The Tc=O bond length in both

complexes is considerably longer (ca 1.75 Å) than the average Tc=O length (ca 1.65 Å) observed in complexes that contain the TcO^{3+} core. The Tc=O stretching modes (790 and 834 cm^{-1} for cyclam and en complexes, respectively) are below the range (1020 – 910 cm^{-1}) observed for $\nu Tc=O$ in TcO^{3+} complexes. It appears that charge neutralization of the Tc center is one of the factors that governs whether a given Tc(V) complex will contain the TcO_3^+ or the $tr-TcO_3^+$ core. The dimethylglyoxime complex is obtained upon the reduction of TcO_4^- by Sn^{2+} in the presence of the ligand. In this compound the tin and technetium are connected by a triple bridge, the separation between metal centers is 3.7 Å²⁷. The tin atom can be viewed as "capping" the three oxygen atoms on one end of the Tc-DMG complex. The oxidation states of tin and technetium in this diamagnetic complex have been assigned as IV and V, respectively²⁷. Mixed tin-technetium complexes could be present in radiopharmaceuticals that are usually prepared using $Sn(II)$ as a reductant.

(c) *Sulphur donor ligands :* Since sulphur containing ligands are often used in ^{99m}Tc radiopharmaceutical preparations, a number of workers have recently undertaken studies of the interaction of sulphur donor ligands with technetium. A variety of complexes have been prepared and characterized: $(Ph_4As)[TcO(dithiolate)_2]$, $(Bu_4N)[TcO(SC(O)CH_2S)_2]$, $[TcO(C_2O_2S_2)_2]^-$, $[TcO(S_2C_2(CN)_2)_2]^-$, $[TcO(tdt)_2]^-$ (tdt=3,4-dimercaptotoluene) and $TcN(S_2CNet_2)_2$, etc¹⁴. Both dithiolato and thioglycolate materials contain the TcO^{3+} core in a distorted square pyramidal environment and the Tc is displaced about 0.76 Å above the plane of the sulphur atoms. The displacement of halide from $[TcOCl_4]^-$ has led to a systematic synthesis of a large variety of *bis*(dithiolato) technetium(V) complexes mentioned above. All these compounds display square pyramidal geometries and exhibit Tc=O stretches in the ir region at 920–980 cm^{-1} ; complexes that contain electron withdrawing substituents on the ligands exhibit Tc=O stretching frequencies towards the higher end of this range. Analogous square pyramidal complexes containing the O,S chelated ligand rather than the S,S chelated ethanedithiolato ligand have recently been prepared¹⁴. A technetium(V) complex containing the $Tc \equiv N^{2+}$ core has also recently been synthesized and characterized²⁸. Hydrazine reduction of TcO_4^- followed by reaction with $Na(S_2CN Et_2)_2$ gives the uncharged nitrido complex $TcN(S_2CNet_2)_2$. Analogous to the *bis*(dithiolato) TcO^{3+} complexes, the geometry of the nitrido complex is square pyramidal with an axial Tc=N bond and the Tc atom is 0.75 Å above the plane of the four sulphur atoms. This complex is isostructural with $ReN(S_2CN Et_2)_2$.

(d) *Phosphorus and arsenic donor ligands :* A number of phosphine and arsine complexes have been described; these all contain (with a few exceptions) technetium in IV or lower oxidation states¹⁴. This is a reflection of both the reducing action of these ligands as well as the "softness"

of the donor atoms that favour stabilization of lower metal oxidation states. The exceptions involve the Tc(V) center which is stabilized either by the presence of special ligands such as diars or by the presence of oxo ligands, e.g., those that result in the formation of the TcO_2^+ core, and thus decrease the effective formal charge on the central metal atom. The octahedral complexes $[Tc(PPh_3)_2Cl_4]$ and $[Tc(AsPh_3)_2Cl_4]$ are produced upon the reaction of PPh_3 or $AsPh_3$ with $(TcCl_4)_n$ in refluxing ethanol. The magnetic moments are respectively 3.92 B.M. and 3.62 B.M. consistent with a Tc(IV) (d^3) species. On the contrary, reaction of 1,2-bis(diphenylphosphine)ethane (dppe) under similar conditions gives the Tc(III) complex, $tr-[Tc(dppe)_2Cl_2]Cl$. When excess dppe is used, further reduction leads to the formation of Tc(II) complexes, $tr-[Tc(dppe)_2X_2]$ ($X=Cl, Br$); these readily oxidize in air to give the Tc(III) analogs. Many of these complexes have been prepared and structurally characterized. Potential use of ^{99m}Tc analogs as heart imaging agents has recently been demonstrated²⁹. The synthesis of $[Tc(diars)_2Cl_4]^+$, an eight-coordinate technetium(V) complex by oxidative addition of molecular chlorine to $tr-[Tc(diars)_2Cl_2]^+$ was described as early as 1960. The diars ligand has previously been shown to stabilize higher coordination numbers. A variety of other complexes with phosphorus and arsenic donor ligands have been described in the literature¹⁴.

(e) *Mixed donor atom ligands*: Several technetium complexes with N,O chelating Schiff bases and aminopolycarboxylate ligands and with other mixed donor atom ligands have been prepared and studied¹⁴. The compounds include $[TcO(Ph-sal)_2Cl]$ and $[TcO(Ph-sal)Cl_2]$ ($Ph-salH=N$ -phenylsalicylideneimine); $(H_2EDTA)Tc(u-o)_2Tc(H_2EDTA) \cdot 5H_2O$, $Ba[Tc(O)EDTA]_2$, $[Tc_2(OC_2H_4N)_4]^{n+}$ and $(Ph_3As[TcOL])$ where $L=RCH(S)COO^-$. In case of the Tc(V) $Ph-salH$ complex, an octahedral structure was suggested in which a phenolic oxygen atom was situated *trans* to the $Tc=O$ bond. The EDTA ligand, depending on reaction conditions forms several different complexes. For example, a strong Tc-Tc bond with a short 2.33 Å distance has been shown to be present in $(H_2EDTA)Tc(u-o)_2Tc(H_2EDTA) \cdot 5H_2O$ and each EDTA coordinates to one technetium by two nitrogen and two oxygen atoms³⁰. Each technetium has an octahedral geometry and perhaps a 4+ oxidation state. Reaction of H_4EDTA with $[TcOCl_4]^-$ in anhydrous DMSO gives $[Tc(O)EDTA]_2^{2-}$, the barium salt of which contains two $[Tc(O)EDTA]^-$ anions, each coordinated to barium ions via four carboxylate bridges¹⁴. The barium is thus eight-coordinate with each technetium atom is seven-coordinate with a distorted pentagonal bipyramidal geometry and the EDTA ligand is hexadentate. This complex illustrates the structural flexibility of the $d^3 TcO^{3+}$ core, which has recently been observed to occur in technetium complexes with 5, 6 and 7 coordination numbers.

2. Structural studies :

Various techniques that have been used for the structure elucidation of technetium compounds include X-ray analysis, elemental analysis and molecular weight determination, ir, Raman, nmr and vis/uv spectroscopy and mass spectroscopy. Definitive structures have been assigned to approximately 65 compounds using X-ray structural analysis³¹. A partial listing of these appears in Table 1. These

TABLE 1—TECHNETIUM COMPOUNDS STRUCTURALLY CHARACTERISED BY SINGLE CRYSTAL X-RAY ANALYSIS^{31, 14, 31}

Compound*	Oxidation state of technetium	Coordination number
$K_2Tc(CN)_6$	I	6
$[trans-Tc(NH_3)_4(NO)(H_2O)]^{2+}$	I	6
$TPP[Tc(CO)_3]_2$	I	6
$TcCl_4 \cdot [(EtO)_2PPh]_4$	II	6
$Tc(diphos)_2Cl_2$	II	6
$[Tc(NO)Br_4]^-$	II	5
$[Tc_2Cl_8]^{2-}$	II, III	6
$TcCl_4(CO)(Me, PPh)_2 \cdot EtOH$	III	7
$[Tc(diars)_2Cl_4]^+$	III	6
$TcCl_2(Me, PPh)_2$	III	6
$TcCl(acac)_2(PPh)_2$	III	6
$Tc_2[OOCMe]_4Cl_2$	III	6
$[Tc(dmpe)_2Cl_2]^+$	III	6
$[Tc(diphos)_2X_2]^+$, X = Cl or Br	III	6
$[Tc(SCN)_6]^{2-}$	III	6
TcO_2	IV	6
$[TcCl_6]^{2-}$	IV	6
$[TcOCl_4]^-$	V	5
$tr-[TcO_2(en)]^+$	V	6
$tr-[TcO_2(cyclam)]^+$	V	6
$[TcO(EDTA)]^-$	V	7
$[TcO(SCH_2CH_2S)_2]^-$	V	5
$[TcO(SCH_2C(O)S)_2]^-$	V	5
$[TcO(SCH_2CH_2O)_2]^-$	V	5
$[Tc(diars)_2Cl_4]^+$	V	8
$[TcO(HBPz_2)_2Cl_2]$	V	6
$Tc(dmgs)(SnCl_4)(OH) \cdot 3H_2O$	V	7
$[TcOF_6]_2$	VI	6
$(Me_2N)_2[TcO_4]$	VI	4
Tc_2O_7	VII	4
Tc_2S_7	VII	4
$Li_2[TcO_5]$	VII	4
$Na_2[TcO_5]$	VII	4
$[Tc(OH)(MDP)]_n$	?	6

*Abbreviations: TPP, tetraphenylporphine; diphos, bis-(1,2-diphenylphosphino)ethane; diars, *o*-phenylenebis-(dimethylarsine); acac, acetylacetonate monoanion; dmpe, bis-(1,2-dimethylphosphino)ethane; en, ethylenediamine; cyclam, 1,4,8,11-tetraazacyclotetradecane; EDTA, ethylenediaminetetraacetate; HBPz₂, hydrotris-(1-pyrazolyl)borate monoanion; dmgs, dimethylglyoxime in unknown protonation state; MDP, methylene diphosphonate in unknown protonation state; Me, methyl; Et, ethyl; Ph, phenyl.

studies provide several results of considerable importance to the design and development of technetium radiopharmaceuticals: (i) A wide range of coordination numbers and geometries is exhibited by complexes of reduced technetium. Even though 6-coordination with an octahedral geometry is most common, the compounds are not restricted to only such structures as generally assumed in the early literature. In simple compounds, a coordination number of four is limited to the 7+ state in the

per salts and the oxide halides; 6-coordination can be assumed by most other lower oxidation states. Five-coordinate compounds with square pyramidal geometry and 7-coordinate compounds with a geometry approximating that of a monocapped octahedron are quite often encountered. (ii) The 5+ oxidation state is more common than previously assumed, when the complexes are prepared using aqueous and aerobic conditions. (iii) A number of complexes contain the Tc(V)=O center such as in TcOCl_4^- and in others, and often bridging oxygen atoms. The likely conclusion is that many technetium radiopharmaceuticals prepared by the reduction of pertechnetate in aqueous media may indeed contain one or two oxo ligands and the properties associated with the chemistry of such linkages. The oxo group in Tc=O compounds exerts a strong *trans*-labilizing effect with the result that the *trans* coordination site is vacant in compounds such as $\text{TcO}(\text{SCH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{S})^{2-}$, $\text{TcO}[\text{SCH}_2\text{C}(\text{O})\text{S}]^{2-}$, TcOCl_4^- etc., or is loosely occupied by a solvent molecule when the compounds are in solution. In $\text{Tc}(\text{HBPz}_3)_2\text{Cl}_2\text{O}$, five coordination is not favoured due to the tridentate nature of the HBPz₃ ligand but the influence of the oxo group leads to a weak *trans* ligand-metal bond as reflected by the *trans* nitrogen atom being 0.2 Å further from technetium than are the two *cis* nitrogen atoms¹⁴. The four equatorial coordination sites *cis* to the oxo ligand are resistant to ligand substitution (in contrast to the labile *trans* site) and thus such structures should provide suitable templates about which to construct radiopharmaceuticals with maximum *in vivo* integrity. The occurrence of tightly bonded Tc(V)=O centers and the different bonding properties of the equatorial and axial sites within these centers may be more commonly involved in routine ^{99m}Tc radiopharmaceuticals than generally recognized. (iv) Technetium can form complexes with metal-metal bonds as exemplified by the structures of $\text{Tc}_2\text{Cl}_8^{3-}$ and $\text{Tc}_2[\text{OCC}(\text{Me})_3]_4\text{Cl}_2$ and this possibility should not be overlooked in the assignment of possible structures. (v) Analogous to the well known nitrosyl-ruthenium complexes, *trans*- $\text{Tc}(\text{NH}_3)_4(\text{NO})(\text{OH}_2)^{2+}$ could represent a large class of nitrosyl-technetium complexes. By virtue of the fact that the NO ligand stabilizes low oxidation states, compounds with Tc-NO centers should be an interesting class to be exploited.

The solid state structure of $[\text{Tc}(\text{OH})\text{MDP}^-]_n$ (and perhaps other bone agent complexes such as pyrophosphate, polyphosphate etc.) shows the compound to be polymeric with technetium centers bridged by MDP and OH (or OH₂) ligands, and MDP ligands in turn bridged by technetium centers. This would indicate that technetium phosphate radiopharmaceuticals may be polymeric mixtures in aqueous solution and not single well defined species. Ligands such as EDTA and DTPA are capable of forming dimeric metal complexes and can also simultaneously coordinate to more than one metal. With the use of tin(II) as a reducing agent in radiopharmaceutical formulations, the possibility of mixed

technetium-tin-ligand complexes cannot be ruled out completely.

Conclusion

Technetium has played a vital role in the rapidly growing field of diagnostic nuclear medicine. A plethora of ^{99m}Tc-labeled compounds is already available for various imaging applications, many others continue to be developed at a rapid pace. The lack of a proper understanding of the exact nature of most earlier technetium radiopharmaceuticals and their mode of action did not significantly hamper the practical usefulness of this radionuclide in diagnostic applications. The ultimate benefits to the patients have been immeasurable. Recently, however, a growing awareness of the need to systematically understand the chemistry and *in vivo* reaction mechanisms of technetium radiopharmaceuticals has resulted in a flurry of research activity in this area. The last five years have seen many important advances including those in the field of technetium coordination chemistry, and in the application of highly sensitive analytical techniques to the fractionation and characterization of complex technetium radiopharmaceutical mixtures. The knowledge that has been acquired will certainly add new and more efficacious ^{99m}Tc radiopharmaceuticals to our existing arsenal and will also result in improvement of the existing agents. Many of the technetium labeled compounds developed earlier included particles and a prior understanding of factors such as the chemical state of technetium and various thermodynamic and kinetic parameters etc. were not crucial to the usefulness of these agents for the intended application. In contrast, effective development and use of many biological compounds and drug molecules labeled with technetium require a thorough understanding of the chemistry, the binding affinities and the effect of the metal on the biological properties of the substrate. Direct binding of technetium to bioactive molecules may be of limited usefulness since in most cases biological behaviour of the labeled compound is drastically altered. In this respect, some of the more recent approaches such as binding technetium to a chelate containing derivative of a biologically active molecule may be of particular value. Work in this direction is already underway and some success has been demonstrated. The major stumbling block has been the synthesis of derivatives of the parent molecule with retention of biological activity.

Recent renewed interest in the area of synthetic and structural coordination chemistry of technetium will undoubtedly play a very important role in the development of improved radiosintigraphic agents. It will be necessary to understand the chemical mechanisms involved in many of these synthetic reactions especially with regard to ligand substitution and oxygen atom transfer redox processes. Such mechanistic studies will complement the large body of knowledge that has slowly been evolving on the synthetic and structural aspects of technetium chemistry.

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